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Need for Branding Higher Educational Institutions

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Abstract

Indian higher education have supplied few of world renowned talents and many of Indians have sources best jobs across the world in the field of medical, engineering, management, arts, commerce, economics and in other fields. At the same time, India is a nation with divided based on the demographic differences, economic standards, social recognition and also based on the urban or rural education standards. Realising these situations, it right time now to realise the need of the stakeholders, they have to brand their institution. With the liberalisation of higher education environment in India, private and foreign universities have started stiffly competing with each other to serve the large size untapped youths. In the process of catering large segment of youths' educational needs to build-in its brand name and reputation to attract more knowledge thirst youths. Branding of higher educational institution in a highly competitive education market is not only need of the hour, but it also supports the HEIs to differentiate their service features and offer very competitive education service. Branding though intangible factor, it support the HEIs to define its accountability and responsibilities towards the learners, society and towards the nation. Brand name of institution exhibits nature of talents pass-out.

Key words: Factors: Higher Educational Institutions, Branding of HEIs, Issues faced by HEIs.

Introduction

Effective workforce and uninterrupted supply of human talents is the need of the hour. Higher educational institutions (HEIs) act as knowledge and skills inculcating factories that actively involved in understanding the needs of the current job market and attempt to cater the need by producing graduates in different disciplines. In the process of catering large segment of youths' educational needs to build-in its brand name and reputation to attract more knowledge thirst youths. Branding of higher educational institution in a highly competitive education market is not only need of the hour, but it also supports the HEIs to differentiate their service features

and offer very competitive education service. Branding though intangible factor, it support the HEIs to define its accountability and responsibilities towards the learners, society and towards the nation. Brand name of institution exhibits nature of talents pass-out.

Major Issues Faced by Higher Educational Institutions in India

Nearly 3.74 crore students sought admission in some or other grade of higher educational institutions. Out of these 3.74 crores students, 3.34 crores of students are admitted in regular (day or evening colleges) and 0.4 crores of students join distance education courses. In addition, to this just two lakh research scholars pass-out from various educational institutions. Most of the

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distance education learners are found to less skilled, less knowledgeable, has poor English communicating skills, poor industrial rapport and highly inflexible for job market need fulfilment.

Forty percentages of teachers working in the higher educational institutions are recruited in temporary or contracted base. And just 33 per cent of the teachers are found to have qualification needed for teaching with an additional Ph.D., degree. Nearly 50 per cent of the teachers recruited are young and less knowledgeable. Similarly, the faculty and students ration are found to be large and teachers cum research scholars' participations in research works or in research paper publication is very minimal.

According to CMIE (Center for Monitoring Indian Economy Pvt. Ltd.) nearly 10 crores graduates pass out every year in the country of which 6.30 per cent of the graduates enter into various industrial sectors as potential work force. Out of the 6.30 crores work force entering the job markets, over 5.35 crores of graduates were able to get some or other kind of job and rests of the 94 lakh graduate are very keen in getting employment as per their aspiration or précised as per their subject specialisation. On the contrary, it has been observed that 17.60 per cent of women graduates and 6.10 per cent of the men graduate youth are found to be unemployed. Poor skill acquired and weak work related knowledge greatly influences the graduate youth in finding appropriate and more remunerating jobs. Besides, all these issues faced by the higher education system in India, one of the health sign nation experience due to the growth of private educational institution is increase in students enrolment from different section of the society and the rural and urban divides is also minimised.

Need to Focus on Branding Higher Educational Institution

With the liberalisation of higher education environment in India, private and foreign universities have started stiffly competing with each other to serve the large size untapped youths. As per OCED (Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development) 71 per cent of students those, who complete school education does not join any higher education course or degree programme. At the same time 70 per cent of women, do not even enter into high school education. As the effect of ever growing potential students' population and mushroom growth of small educational edupreneurs have forced the big institutions to focus more on brand building activities. Brand building process of educational institutions is possible only active support of various level stakeholders (pass-out graduates, faculties, parents, society and the Government). Parents play a prime role in influencing the college joining decisions of their adult children.

Factors Determining Branding of Higher Educational Institution

In India, students' selection of higher educational institution for the further study is influenced by number of factors. Students in general prefer to join Engineering, Medical, Sports and Commerce degree course. Brand building of higher educational institutions (Colleges and Universities) is more people driven rather than any symbol, logo or other promotional activities.

In true sense, trust, services offered, faculties support, performance of the institution in the past and recognition earned among the people in the society act as key factors. In general it has been observed that higher educational institution try to materialize the reputation earned by them

CHART: 1
BRANDING OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Source: Pictograph Developed for the Study

over the years to attract new students (customers) and promote their educational products or packages.

Conclusion

Indian higher education have supplied few of world renowned talents and many of Indians have sources best jobs across the world in the field of medical, engineering, management, arts, commerce, economics and in other fields. At the same time, India is a nation with divided based on the demographic differences, economic standards, social recognition and also based

on the urban or rural education standards. Realising these situations, it right time now to realise the need of the stakeholders, they have to brand their institution. Higher education institution should not only focus on enrolling more number of students, rather they have to focus on the knowledge and skills to be inculcated among the youth. As this strategic move of the higher educational institutions will support them in enrolling students' based on their needs and not based on the marks score by them. Past experience have proved that interest based learning

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environment always give more productive results (i.e., production valuable work force) compared to enrolling uninterested passive degree seekers. As cross the globe debate between quantity and quality always prevails.

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